

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THE FOLLOWING AWARD IS GIVEN TO

Jahanvi Chaudhary

This certificate is given for organising the Basic Research workshop conducted in hybrid mode in Kyiv Medical University, Katowice, Poland.

Awarded March 2nd, 2024

Dr. Indraneil Mukherjee

DR. INDRANEIL MUKHERJEE
FOUNDER & CHAIRMAN

Dr. Palak Dutta

DR. PALAK DUTTA
FOUNDER & CHIEF
ORGANISER

Dr. Rohit Ganduboina

DR. ROHIT GANDUBOINA
FOUNDER

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THE FOLLOWING AWARD IS GIVEN TO

Kritik Gaur

This certificate is given for organising the Basic Research workshop conducted in hybrid mode in Kyiv Medical University, Katowice, Poland.

Awarded March 2nd, 2024

Dr. Indraneil Mukherjee
DR. INDRANEIL MUKHERJEE
FOUNDER & CHAIRMAN

Dr. Palak Dutta
DR. PALAK DUTTA
FOUNDER & CHIEF
ORGANISER

Dr. Rohit Ganduboina
DR. ROHIT GANDUBOINA
FOUNDER

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THE FOLLOWING AWARD IS GIVEN TO

Vikash Kumar Kesari

This certificate is given for organising the Basic Research workshop conducted in hybrid mode in Kyiv Medical University, Katowice, Poland.

Awarded March 2nd, 2024

Dr. Indraneil Mukherjee

DR. INDRANEIL MUKHERJEE

FOUNDER & CHAIRMAN

Dr. Palak Dutta

DR. PALAK DUTTA

FOUNDER & CHIEF
ORGANISER

Dr. Rohit Ganduboina

DR. ROHIT GANDUBOINA

FOUNDER